

Integrating Carbon Farming Practices in Potato Cropping Systems: A Pathway to Sustainable Agriculture

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Carbon farming is a management practice that aims at increasing the amount of carbon stored in plant biomass and soils. Farmers are learning about and applying carbon farming methods in the context of the new paradigm with increasing frequency. Here, we provide an overview and describe the implications of promising carbon farming practices in potato production, one of the most important food crops worldwide. Conservation tillage, organic fertilization and cover cropping are practices that result in important increases in soil organic carbon (SOC) levels while reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Conservation tillage restricts soil disturbance and promotes better carbon retention within the soil profile. Furthermore, cover crops when used as green manure, increase SOC inventories in agricultural soils. Application of organic amendments, such as biochar and compost, can enhance soil carbon sequestration and encourage plant growth. These practices provide sustainable techniques for soil restoration and carbon sequestration, thereby improving the resilience of potato cropping systems.

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